

Functional analysis of the copy 1 of the *fixNOQP* operon of *Ensifer meliloti* under free-living micro-oxic and symbiotic conditions

M.J. Torres, A. Hidalgo-García, E.J. Bedmar, M.J. Delgado

Estación Experimental del Zaidin, CSIC, Granada, Spain

Abstract

Aim

In this work, phenotypic analyses of a *Ensifer meliloti fixNI* mutant under free-living and symbiotic conditions have been carried out.

Methods and Results

Ensifer meliloti fixNI mutant showed a defect in growth as well as in TMPD-dependent oxidase activity when cells were incubated under micro-oxic conditions. Furthermore, haem *c* staining analyses of a *fixNI* and a *fixPI* mutant identified two membrane-bound *c*-type cytochromes of 27 and 32 kDa, present in microaerobically grown cells and in bacteroids, as the FixO and FixP components of the *E. meliloti cbb₃* oxidase. Under symbiotic conditions, *fixNI* mutant showed a clear nitrogen fixation defect in alfalfa plants that were grown in an N-free nutrient solution during 3 weeks. However, in plants grown for a longer period, *fixNOQP1* copy was not indispensable for symbiotic nitrogen fixation.

Conclusions

The copy 1 of the *fixNOQP* operon is involved in *E. meliloti* respiration and growth under micro-oxic conditions as well as in the expression of the FixO and FixP components of the *cbb₃* oxidase present in free-living microaerobic cultures and in bacteroids. This copy is important for nitrogen fixation during the early steps of the symbiosis.

Significance and Impact of the Study

It is the first time that a functional analysis of the *E. meliloti* copy 1 of the *fixNOQP* operon is performed. In this work, the cytochromes *c* that constitute the *cbb₃* oxidase operating in free-living micro-oxic cultures and in bacteroids of *E. meliloti* have been identified.

Keywords

cytochromes, *fixNOQP*, micro-oxic conditions, respiration, symbiosis.

Introduction

Soil bacteria, collectively known as rhizobia, form nitrogen-fixing nodules on the roots of leguminous plants. They have been intensively studied because of their agronomic importance and the inherent biological interest of their complex interactions with their host plants. The establishment of an effective symbiotic association between rhizobia and legumes is a highly specific and complex developmental process, in which both partners undergo differentiation in a concerted way (reviewed by Jones *et al.* [2007](#); Oldroyd and Downie [2008](#); Oldroyd *et al.* [2011](#)). Following invasion of the plant cells via a complex signalling pathway between bacteria and plant, rhizobia stop dividing and undergo differentiation into nitrogen-fixing bacteroids. The activity of the nitrogen-reducing enzyme nitrogenase requires a high rate of oxygen respiration to supply the energy demands of the nitrogen reduction process. However, oxygen irreversibly inactivates the nitrogenase complex. These conflicting demands are met by controlling oxygen flux to the infected plant cells through an oxygen diffusion barrier, which greatly limits permeability to oxygen (Minchin *et al.* [2008](#)). Oxygen is then delivered to the bacteroids by the plant oxygen carrier, leghaemoglobin, present exclusively in the nodule (Downie [2005](#)). To cope with the low ambient oxygen concentration in the nodule (10–50 nmol l⁻¹ O₂), nitrogen-fixing bacteroids induce a high-affinity cytochrome *cbb*₃-type oxidase (Delgado *et al.* [1998](#)). Genes encoding the *cbb*₃ complex were initially isolated from rhizobia and named *fixNOQP* due to its requirement for symbiotic nitrogen fixation (Preisig *et al.* [1996](#)). Since then, orthologous genes called *ccoNOQP* were identified in other Proteobacteria including photosynthetic and pathogenic bacteria (reviewed in Cosseau and Batut [2004](#); Bueno *et al.* [2012](#); Ekici *et al.* [2012](#)).

Cytochrome *cbb*₃ oxidases have been purified from several organisms, including *Paracoccus denitrificans*, *Rhodobacter sphaeroides*, *Rhodobacter capsulatus* and *Bradyrhizobium japonicum* (reviewed in Pitcher and Watmough [2004](#)). Subunit I (FixN or CcoN) is a membrane-integral *b*-type and copper-containing cytochrome. Electrons are delivered to the haem/Cu_B site on subunit I via the membrane-anchored monohaem *c*- and dihaem *c*-type cytochromes FixO/CcoO and FixP/CcoP, which constitute subunits II and III, respectively (Buschmann *et al.* [2010](#)). FixQ or CcoQ is required for optimal oxidase activity, because it stabilizes the interaction of CcoP with the CcoNO core complex, leading subsequently to the formation of the active 230-kDa complex (Peters *et al.* [2008](#)). The biogenesis of this oxidase depends on the *ccoGHIS* gene products, which are proposed to be specifically required for cofactor insertion and maturation of *cbb*₃-type cytochrome *c* oxidases (Kulajta *et al.* [2006](#); Pawlik *et al.* [2010](#)). Several additional proteins including SenC (Swem *et al.* [2005](#)), PCu_AC (Banci *et al.* [2005](#); Abriata *et al.* [2008](#); Serventi *et al.* [2012](#)), DsbA (Deshmukh *et al.* [2003](#)) and CcoA (Ekici *et al.* [2012](#)) might be also involved in *cbb*₃ biogenesis.

Ensifer meliloti is an aerobic soil bacterium that establishes symbiotic N₂-fixing associations with plants of the genera *Medicago*, *Melilotus* and *Trigonella*. The expression of *E. meliloti* genes required for nitrogen fixation and for microaerobic respiration is coordinated by *fixLJ* and *fixK* genes, which are conserved among rhizobia (Fischer [1994](#); Dixon and Kahn [2004](#)). Under oxygen-limiting conditions, FixL autophosphorylates and transmits phosphate to the FixJ response regulator. Once phosphorylated, FixJ activates transcription of the *nifA* and *fixK* genes, which induce expression of *nif* and *fix* genes, respectively (Reyrat *et al.* [1993](#)). A set of publications has demonstrated that *fixT* and *fixM* are also targets of FixJ (Ampe *et al.* [2003](#); Barnett *et al.* [2004](#); Becker *et al.* [2004](#); Bobik *et al.* [2006](#);

Meilhoc *et al.* [2010](#)). While *fixT* negatively affects expression of FixLJ-dependent genes by inhibiting FixL autophosphorylation (Garnerone *et al.* [1999](#)), *fixM* encodes a flavoprotein that modulates inhibition by 5-aminoimidazole-4-carboxamide nucleotide (AICAR) or 5'adenosine monophosphate (5'AMP) of respiratory and nitrogen fixation genes expression in *E. meliloti* (Cosseau *et al.* [2002](#)).

Inspection of the *E. meliloti* 1021 genome sequence shows a composite architecture, consisting of three replicons with distinctive structure and function: a 3.65-Mb chromosome and two megaplasmids, pSymA (1.35 Mb) and pSymB (1.68 Mb) (Galibert *et al.* [2001](#)). pSymA contains a large fraction of genes known to be specifically involved in symbiosis such as genes involved in nodulation or in nitrogen fixation process, as well as genes involved in microaerobic metabolism or in denitrification (Barnett *et al.* [2001](#)). A 290-kilobase (kb) region of pSymA contains nodulation genes as well as genes involved in nitrogen fixation (*nif* and *fix*) and it carries repeated sequences (Renalier *et al.* [1987](#)). One of these reiterated sequences had been identified as part of a cluster of *fix* genes located 220 kb downstream of *nifHDK* genes and contains regulatory genes (*fixLJ*, *fixT1*, *fixK1*, *fixM*), *fixGHIS* genes, as well as a copy of the *fixNOQP* operon (*fixNOQP1*) (Fig. [1](#)). The second *fix* cluster maps 40 kb upstream of the *nifHDK* genes and carries another copy of the *fixNOQP* operon (*fixNOQP2*), regulatory genes (*fixT2*, *fixK2*) as well as a *nod* locus (Renalier *et al.* [1987](#)). Both *fixNOQP* copies are closely related because they encode for proteins having a 95% homology in their respective sequences. In the pSymA genome, there is a third copy of the *fixNOQP* operon (*fixNOQP3*), which only presents a 61% homology with the other two copies. Neither genes related with nodulation nor nitrogen fixation is located in the *fixNOQP3* genomic context (Fig. [1](#), <http://genome.microbedb.jp/rhizobase/>).

Figure 1

Genomic context of the three copies of the *fixNOQP* operon in the symbiotic plasmid pSymA of *Ensifer meliloti*

Recent transcriptomic analyses have shown that *fixNOQP1* genes of *E. meliloti* are induced under microaerobic free-living and symbiotic conditions (Becker *et al.* [2004](#)). Furthermore, *fixNOQP1* genes have been identified as targets of FixK and FixJ in response to low-oxygen conditions (Bobik *et al.* [2006](#); Meilhoc *et al.* [2010](#)). However, up-to-date functional analyses of these genes are missing. The involvement of *fixNOQP1* genes in free-living respiration and symbiotic nitrogen fixation has been investigated in this work.

Materials and methods

Bacterial strains, growth conditions and recombinant DNA methods

Bacterial strains used in this work are *E. meliloti* wild-type strain 1021 (Meade *et al.* [1982](#)), *fixP1* mutant strain G1PELR32C12 RhizoGATE (Becker *et al.* [2009](#)) and *fixN1* mutant strain 2104 (this work). The *fixN1* gene was mutated by performing gene-directed mutagenesis by marker exchange. A PCR fragment of 1.5 kb containing the *fixN1* coding region of Sm1021 was subcloned into pK18 mobsac (Schäfer *et al.* [1994](#)) to obtain plasmid pBG2104. Finally, the 2-kb fragment (Ω Spc/Sm interposon) of pHP45 Ω (Prentki and Krisch [1984](#)) was inserted at the unique *NruI* site located 683 bp downstream of the FixN1 start codon in the 1.5-kb PCR fragment. The resulting plasmid pBG2104 Ω was transferred via conjugation into *E. meliloti* 1021 using *Escherichia coli* S17-1 carrying pBG2104 Ω as donor. Double recombination events were favoured by growth on agar plates containing sucrose. Mutant strains resistant to spectinomycin/streptomycin but sensitive to kanamycin were checked by Southern hybridization experiments (data not shown) for correct replacement of the wild-type fragment by the Ω interposon. The mutant derivative 2104, used in this study, was obtained. Total and plasmid DNA isolation, digestion with restriction enzymes, cloning, agarose gel electrophoresis and *Escherichia coli* transformation were performed using standard protocols (Sambrook and Russell [2004](#)). Enzymes used for DNA restriction and modification were purchased from Fermentas (Vilnius, Lithuania) and were used according to the instructions of the manufacturer. For Southern hybridizations, DNA was digested with appropriate restriction enzymes, electrophoresed in 1% (wt/vol) agarose gels and blotted onto nylon (Hybond N+). Hybridization was carried out under high stringency conditions using RapidHyb buffer (Amersham, Bucks, UK). Specific probes were normally obtained by PCR and were labelled with $\alpha^{32}\text{P}$ -CTP by random priming, using Amersham's Rediprime system.

Ensifer meliloti strains were routinely grown in medium TY (Tryptone Yeast, Beringer [1974](#)) at 30°C. For determinations of growth rates, respiratory activity and haem *c* staining in free-living conditions, cells were grown in minimal medium (Robertsen *et al.* [1981](#)). Cell growth under micro-oxic conditions was performed by fluxing a gas mixture of 2% O₂ and 98% Ar into the cultures. Initial optical density at 600 nm of the cultures was about 0.1. Antibiotics were added to *E. meliloti* cultures at the following concentrations ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$): spectinomycin, 200; streptomycin, 200, kanamycin, 100. *Escherichia coli* strains were cultured in Luria–Bertani medium (Miller [1972](#)) at 37°C. *Escherichia coli* DH5 α (Stratagene, Heidelberg, Germany) was used as host in standard cloning procedures and *Escherichia coli* S17-1 (Simon *et al.* [1983](#)) served as the donor in conjugative plasmid transfer. The antibiotics used were ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) ampicillin, 200; streptomycin, 20; spectinomycin, 20; and kanamycin, 25.

Plant growth conditions

Alfalfa (*Medicago sativa*, var. Aragón) seeds were surface-sterilized by immersing in 2.5% HgCl₂ for 9 min. Then, seeds were washed with sterile water and germinated on wet filter paper in Petri dishes in darkness at 28°C for 36 h. Selected seedlings were planted in 1-l autoclaved Leonard jars (Leonard [1943](#)) filled with vermiculite and containing nitrogen-free mineral solution (Rigaud and Puppo [1975](#)). Seeds (eight per jar) were inoculated at sowing with 1 ml of a single bacterial strain (10⁸ cells per ml). Plants were grown in controlled environmental chambers (night/day temperature, 19/25°C; photoperiod, 16/8 h; PPF, 400 μmol m⁻² s⁻¹; and relative humidity, 60–70%). For nodulation kinetics assays, germinated seeds were transferred into autoclaved glass tubes containing 5 ml of the N-free nutrient solution and inoculated with approximately 1 × 10⁸ of a single bacterial strain. Each tube, covered with a cotton stopper, was incubated in a growth chamber. After inoculation, the number of nodulated plants and the number of nodules per plant were recorded daily.

Plant assays

Shoots (separated from roots at the cotyledonary node) were dried to a constant weight at 60°C. Dry weight on shoots (SDW), height on shoots (SH) and roots (RH) and nodule fresh weight (NFW) were determined per plant. Nodules were harvested from 7-week-old plants and were frozen into liquid nitrogen and stored at –80°C. Total nitrogen was measured in oven-dried shoots weighed and grounded in an IKA A 11 basic analytical mill (Rose Scientific Ltd., Alberta, Canada). Total nitrogen was determined using a LECO TruSpec CN Elemental Analyzer (LECO Corp., St Joseph, MI, USA).

Bacterial respiratory capacity

Oxygen uptake was determined as described by Marroqui *et al.* ([2001](#)). Cells were harvested after 48 h of growth at 30°C in minimum medium, washed and resuspended in 1 ml 25 mmol l⁻¹ potassium phosphate buffer (pH 7.0). The oxygen uptake at 21°C was measured using a Clark-type oxygen electrode (Hansatech, Norkfolk, UK) after addition of 2 mmol l⁻¹ N,N,N',N'-tetramethyl-*p*-phenylenediamine (TMPD) and 4 mmol l⁻¹ sodium ascorbate to the cellular suspension (0.15–0.25 mg protein). The time taken to consume the oxygen present in the system was used to calculate the rate of TMPD-dependent oxygen consumption.

Membrane extraction, cells fractionation and haem *c* staining

Cells of *E. meliloti* grown aerobically in 150 ml TY medium were harvested by centrifugation at 12 000 *g* for 5 min, washed twice with minimal medium, resuspended in 500 ml of the same medium and finally incubated under low-oxygen conditions for 2 days. Bacteroids from nodules were prepared as previously described by Mesa *et al.* ([2004](#)). Briefly, 1 g of fresh nodules was ground in 7.5 ml Tris/HCl (pH 7.5) supplemented with 250 mmol l⁻¹ mannitol. The homogenate was filtered through four layers of cheesecloth and was centrifuged at 250 *g* at 4°C for 5 min to remove nodule debris. The resulting supernatant was centrifuged twice at 12 000 *g* at 4°C for 10 min and was washed twice in 50 mmol l⁻¹ potassium phosphate buffer (pH 7). Free-living cells and bacteroids were resuspended in 3 ml of 50 mmol l⁻¹ potassium phosphate buffer (pH 7) containing 100 μmol l⁻¹ 4-(2-aminoethyl) benzene-sulfonyl fluoride hydrochloride (ABSF), RNase (20 μg ml⁻¹), and DNase I (20 μg ml⁻¹). Cells were disrupted using a French pressure cell (SLM Aminco, Jessup, MD, USA). The cell extract was centrifuged at 20 000 *g* for 20 min to remove unbroken cells, and the supernatant was then centrifuged at 140 000 *g* for 1 h. The membrane pellet was resuspended in 100 μl of the

same buffer. Membrane protein aliquots (from free-living cells or bacteroids) were diluted in sample buffer [124 mmol l⁻¹ Tris/HCl, pH 7.0, 20% glycerol, 4.6% sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) and 50 mmol l⁻¹ 2-mercaptoethanol] and incubated at room temperature for 10 min. Membrane proteins were separated at 4°C in SDS-12% polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis, transferred to a nitrocellulose membrane and stained for haem-dependent peroxidase activity as described previously (Vargas *et al.* 1993) using the chemiluminescence detection kit ‘SuperSignal’ (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Pierce, IL, USA).

Analytical methods

The protein concentration was estimated using the Bio-Rad assay (Bio-Rad Laboratories, Richmond, CA, USA) with a standard curve of varying bovine serum albumin concentrations.

Results

Free-living growth rates and respiratory capacity

To investigate the involvement of the *cbb*₃ oxidase encoded by the *fixNOQP1* operon in free-living growth, a *fixNI* mutant was incubated aerobically and microaerobically (2% O₂) in minimum medium. Growth was determined by monitoring the optical density at 600 nm (OD₆₀₀). After incubation under aerobic conditions, no significant differences were observed in growth rates of the wild-type and the *fixNI* mutant (Fig. 2). However, the *fixNI* mutant showed a defect in growth, reaching an OD₆₀₀ of only 0.5 compared to that of 0.9 determined in wild-type (WT) cells after 72-h incubation under micro-oxic conditions (Fig. 2). Cytochrome *c*-dependent oxygen consumption was measured in the WT strain and the *fixNI* deficient mutant using ascorbate-reduced TMPD as a nonphysiological electron donor (Fig. 3). Independently of the strain, TMPD oxidase activity observed in cells grown aerobically was lower than that observed in cells grown under oxygen-limiting conditions. This difference could be due to the induction under oxygen-limiting conditions of high-affinity cytochrome *c* oxidases, which have greater activity than those induced in aerobic cultures that have low affinity for oxygen. Alternatively, it might be possible that the affinity for TMPD/ascorbate is higher in micro-oxic cultures than in oxically grown cells. Under aerobic conditions, the *fixNI* mutant showed levels of TMPD oxidase activity similar to those of the WT strain (Fig. 3). However, when cells were incubated under micro-oxic conditions, oxygen consumption rates of *fixNI* cells were approximately about 37% lower than those of WT cells after 48 h growth (Fig. 3). The decrease in TMPD-dependent oxidase activity observed in the *fixNI* mutant under oxygen-limiting conditions compared to that observed in the wild-type strain could explain the defect of *fixNI* growth under these conditions (Figs 2 and 3).

Figure 2

Growth of wild-type *Ensifer meliloti* 1021 (●, ○) and *fixNI* mutant (■, □) strains in minimal medium under aerobic conditions (closed symbols) or micro-oxic conditions (open symbols). Error bars represent standard deviation of data from at least two different cultures assayed in triplicate.

Figure 3

TMPD-dependent oxygen consumption capacity by whole cells of wild-type *Ensifer meliloti* 1021 (grey bars) and *fixNI* mutant (white bars) after 48 h growth in minimal medium under aerobic or micro-oxic conditions. Error bars represent standard deviation of data from at least two different cultures assayed in triplicate.

Haem *c* staining analyses

Iron present in haem groups that are covalently bound to proteins, such as *c*-type cytochromes, can be visualized by using a sensitive chemiluminescence assay (Vargas *et al.* 1993). Haem *c* staining of electrophoretically fractionated membrane preparations of *E. meliloti* 1021 grown under aerobic conditions revealed two bands of about 40 and 33 kDa (Fig. 4a, lane 1). In the membrane fractions of WT cells grown under micro-oxic conditions, two additional stained bands at kDa values of 32 and 27 could be detected (Fig. 4a, lane 2). Profiles from the membrane fraction of microaerobically grown cells of the *fixNI* mutant showed that it lacked the *c*-type cytochromes of about 32 and 27 kDa (Fig. 4a, lane 3). Similarly, we could not detect the 32-kDa band in membrane fractions of a *fixPI* mutant (Fig. 4a, lane 4). However, the *c*-type cytochrome of about 27 kDa was present in membranes of the *fixPI* mutant (Fig. 4a, lane 4). These results indicate that the 27-kDa and the 32-kDa *c*-type cytochromes only appear in *E. meliloti* cells grown under low-oxygen conditions and they correspond to the *E. meliloti* FixP1 and FixO1 components, respectively, of the *cbb₃*-type cytochrome oxidase encoded by the *fixNOQP1* operon. The identification of the haem-stainable bands of approximately 40 and 33 kDa present in membranes of wild-type cells grown under both aerobic and microaerobic conditions as well as in those of *fixNI* and *fixPI* cells grown under microaerobic conditions is at the moment unknown.

Figure 4

(a) Haem *c*-stained proteins in membranes prepared from wild-type *Ensifer meliloti* 1021 (lanes 1 and 2), *fixNI* mutant (lane 3) and *fixPI* mutant (lane 4). Cells were incubated aerobically (lane 1) or microaerobically (lanes 2, 3 and 4) in minimal medium. (b) Haem *c*-stained proteins in membranes of bacteroids of wild-type *E. meliloti* 1021 (lane 1) and *fixNI* mutant (lane 2). Nodules were collected from 7-week-grown alfalfa plants.

In (a and b), each lane contains about 20 mg membrane proteins. Apparent masses of the proteins (kDa) are shown at the left margin.

In the membrane fraction of bacteroids, the total amount of haem-stained proteins was considerably higher than that seen with membranes from free-living cells (Fig. 4a,b). Apparent masses of these haem-stained proteins suggest that they correspond to the 40, 33, 32 and 27 *c*-type cytochromes detected in membranes of free-living microaerobically grown cells of the WT strain (Fig. 4a lane 2 and b, lane 1). These results indicate that, as observed in microaerobically grown cells, bacteroids from *E. meliloti* 1021 produce the 32 and 27-kDa *c*-type cytochromes, corresponding to FixP and FixO components of the *cbb*₃ cytochrome oxidase. By contrast to free-living conditions, the band of about 33 kDa migrated together with FixP in membranes of bacteroids. Consequently, we could not demonstrate the absence of the 32-kDa FixP *c*-type cytochrome in membranes of *fixNI* bacteroids (Fig. 4a,b). However, the *c*-type cytochrome of 27 kDa corresponding to FixO was not detected in membranes from bacteroids of the *fixNI* mutant (Fig. 4b, lane 2).

Symbiotic phenotype of the *fixNI* mutant

The *fixNI* mutant was used to inoculate alfalfa plants that were grown in N-free nutrient solution. After 3 weeks, the alfalfa plants that were not inoculated with any *E. meliloti* strains were short and turning yellow. The alfalfa plants that were inoculated with *E. meliloti* 1021 strain were tall and green and therefore had established an efficient symbiosis. However, most of the alfalfa plants inoculated with the *fixNI* mutant were shorter and lighter green than those inoculated with the wild-type strain showing signs of nitrogen deficiency (Fig. 5). To further confirm the symbiotic deficiency of the *fixNI* mutant, physiological parameters, including nodulation capacity, shoot dry weight (SDW), total nitrogen content (N), and shoot and roots height (SH and RH), were measured in plants inoculated with the wild-type or the *fixNI* mutant (Table 1). Noninoculated alfalfa plants had no nodules (data not shown). Plants inoculated with either the wild-type or the *fixNI* mutant had an average of four nodules per plant after 3 weeks (Table 1). Similarly, 100% of the plants were nodulated by strains 1021 or *fixNI* (Table 1). However, plants inoculated with the *fixNI* mutant displayed significant decreases in SDW and [N] compared to those inoculated with the wild-type strain (38 and 30%, respectively) (Table 1). Similarly, SH and RH of plants inoculated with the *fixNI* mutant were significantly lower than those of plants inoculated with *E. meliloti* 1021 (46 and 52%, respectively) (Table 1). Taken together, these results demonstrate that *E. meliloti fixNI* mutant has not any defect in nodulation efficiency. However, this mutant shows a clear defect in symbiotic nitrogen fixation.

Table 1. Shoot dry weight (SDW), nitrogen content [N], shoot height (SH), root height (RH), nodules number per plant (NNP) and percentage of nodulated plants (NP) inoculated with the wild-type *Ensifer meliloti* 1021 strain and the *fixNI* mutant derivative. Plants were grown for 3 weeks after inoculation. Data are means with the standard error in parentheses from at least 100 different plants assayed in at least three independent experiments. In the columns, values followed by the different lower-case letter are significantly different as determined by the Tukey HSD test at $P \leq 0.05$

	SDW plant ⁻¹)	(mg [N] (mg N plant ⁻¹)	SH (cm plant ⁻¹)	RH (cm plant ⁻¹)	NNP	NP
WT	13.9 (1.6)a	0.570 (0.040)a	9.31 (1.24)a	32.95 (5.74)a	4.36 (0.42)a	100%a
<i>fixN</i>	8.7 (0.7)b	0.399 (0.057)b	5.07 (0.96)b	15.99 (2.34)b	3.82 (0.52)a	100%a

Figure 5

Nitrogen fixation–dependent growth of alfalfa plants noninoculated (a) or inoculated with *Ensifer meliloti* wild-type (c) or *fixN1* mutant (b) 21 days after inoculation.

To confirm further the symbiotic nitrogen fixation deficiency of the *fixN1* mutant, alfalfa plants inoculated with either the wild-type or the *fixN1* mutant were grown over a longer period. Surprisingly, after 7 weeks, alfalfa plants inoculated with *fixN1* were tall and green showing a similar aspect as those inoculated with the wild-type strain (Fig. 6). To confirm these observations, SDW, [N] and nodulation capacity measured as nodule fresh weight (NFW) were determined in alfalfa plants after 7 weeks growth. As shown in Table 2, plants inoculated with the *fixN1* mutant had similar SDW, [N] and NFW than plants inoculated with the WT strain.

Table 2. Shoot dry weight (SDW), nitrogen content [N] and nodule fresh weight (NFW) of plants inoculated with the wild-type *Ensifer meliloti* 1021 and *fixN1* mutant derivative. Plants were grown for 7 weeks after inoculation. Data are means with the standard error in parentheses from at least 70 different plants, assayed in at least three independent experiments. In the columns, values followed by the same lower-case letter are not significantly different as determined by the Tukey HSD test at $P \leq 0.05$

	SDW (mg plant ⁻¹)	[N] (mg N plant ⁻¹)	NFW (mg plant ⁻¹)
WT	281.1 (47.9) a	11.585 (0.564) a	35.5 (3.5) a
<i>fixN</i>	264.6 (52.0) a	11.616 (1.186) a	42.0 (4.0) a

Figure 6

Nitrogen fixation–dependent growth of alfalfa plants inoculated with *Ensifer meliloti* wild-type (a) or *fixN1* mutant (b) 49 days after inoculation.

Discussion

The actual physiological role of the high-affinity *cbb₃* oxidase encoded by the *fixNOQP* operon in symbiotic nitrogen fixation has been investigated in many rhizobial species such as *B. japonicum* (Preisig *et al.* [1993](#), [1996](#)), *Azorhizobium caulinodans* (Mandon *et al.* [1993](#), [1994](#)), *Rhizobium leguminosarum* (Schlüter *et al.* [1997](#)) and *Rhizobium etli* (Girard *et al.* [2000](#); Granados-Baeza *et al.* [2007](#)). While *B. japonicum* and *A. caulinodans* have only one copy of the *fixNOQP* operon, reiteration of these genes has been reported in *Rh. leguminosarum* bv. *viciae* (Schlüter *et al.* [1997](#)), *Rh. etli* (Girard *et al.* [2000](#)) and in *Mesorhizobium loti* (Uchiumi *et al.* [2004](#)). In *E. meliloti*, three copies of the *fixNOQP* operon have been identified (Fig. 1, <http://genome.kazusa.or.jp/rhizobase/>). The first copy is located in a DNA region containing also the whole set of regulatory genes (*fixLJ*, *fixK*, *fixT* and *fixM*) required for microaerobic respiration and nitrogen fixation. These observations suggest that copy 1 of *E. meliloti fixNOQP* genes is the potential candidate to support respiration under free-living and symbiotic conditions.

Free-living experiments have demonstrated the involvement of *fixNOQP1* genes in respiration and growth of *E. meliloti* cells under low-oxygen conditions. Furthermore, chemiluminescent staining analyses used to visualize proteins that contain *c*-type cytochromes have demonstrated by the first time that the two membrane-bound *c*-type cytochromes, with molecular masses of 27 and 32 kDa, detected in microaerobically grown cells, correspond to the FixO and FixP components of the *E. meliloti cbb₃* oxidase. The absence of these cytochromes in the *fixNI* mutant suggests that copy 1 of *fixNOQP* operon is the sole functional copy required to express the cytochrome *cbb₃* terminal oxidase under free-living micro-oxic conditions. Supporting our findings, it has been recently proposed that *fixNOQP1* genes are regulated by FixJ under both micro-oxic free-living and symbiotic conditions, whereas copy 2, which is located next to the NifA regulon, was only detectable in bacteroids (Bobik *et al.* [2006](#)). With respect to *fixNOQP3* operon, it was not induced under either microaerobic or symbiotic conditions (Bobik *et al.* [2006](#)). Two genes from the *fixNOQP₃* operon have been showed partially *phoB* regulated (Krol and Becker [2004](#)). It has been proposed that the three copies of *fixNOQP* operon undergo differential regulation in *E. meliloti* (Bobik *et al.* [2006](#)) suggesting a different physiological role for them. It has been shown in *M. loti* that the *fixNOQP* copy located out of the symbiotic island functions preferentially in microaerobic environments, whereas bacteroids likely use two copies for symbiotic respiration (Uchiumi *et al.* [2004](#)).

The haem-stained band of about 33 kDa also present in membranes of *E. meliloti* microaerobically grown cells is the predicted size for cytochrome *c₁* that is a component of *bc₁* complex. In *B. japonicum* (Thony-Meyer *et al.* [1989](#)) and in *Rh. leguminosarum* (Wu *et al.* [1996](#)), it has been demonstrated that *bc₁* complex transfers electrons to the *cbb₃* oxidase and is essential for symbiotic nitrogen fixation. The 40-kDa protein band had been previously detected in *E. meliloti* membranes by Yurgel *et al.* ([2007](#)). A search for *E. meliloti* genes predicted to produce proteins that contain the CXXCH haem-binding motif and are in this molecular mass range allowed these authors to propose SMb21367 (*cycA*) or SMc02858 (a 41-kDa DnaJ-type protein) as potential candidates.

In this work, we have also investigated the function of the *fixNOQP1* operon under symbiotic conditions. Nodulation kinetics, plant dry weigh and total nitrogen results in plants inoculated with the *fixNI* mutant and grown for 21 days in N-free nutrient solution clearly suggest that this copy is required for optimal fixation of nitrogen. However, symbiotic performance of alfalfa plants inoculated with the *fixNI* mutant and grown for 49 days was very similar to the plants inoculated with the wild-type strain. It might be possible that for longer growth periods, the other copies of *fixNOQP* are functional in symbiotic conditions. These results agree with those published previously by Trzebiatowski *et al.* ([2001](#)) where a *E. meliloti* strain carrying a Tn5-1063 insertion within *fixN* was symbiotically proficient, suggesting that a second functional copy of *fixN* could be involved in symbiotic nitrogen fixation. In *Rh. leguminosarum* bv. *viciae*, both copies of *fixNOQP* genes are required for optimal nitrogen fixation (Schlüter *et al.* [1997](#)). However, in *Rh. etli*, a mutation in the *fixN* of plasmid d (but not in that of plasmid f) was severely affected, indicating a differential role for these reiterations in nitrogen fixation (Granados-Baeza *et al.* [2007](#)).

The absence of the 27-kDa *c*-type cytochrome corresponding to FixO in membranes of bacteroids from nodules of 7-week-old plants inoculated with the *fixNI* mutant suggests that the copy one of *fixNOQP* genes is the sole functional copy responsible for expression of FixP and FixO proteins in bacteroids. By contrary to our observations, transcriptomic

analyses have demonstrated expression of the copy 2 of *E. meliloti fixNOQP* operon in bacteroids (Bobik *et al.* [2006](#)). However, these authors found that levels of induction of *fixNOQP2* genes by low-oxygen conditions under free-living conditions is only twofold compared to fivefold induction of *fixNOQP1* genes relative to expression levels under oxic conditions (Bobik *et al.* [2006](#)). Hence, we do not exclude that the lack of detection of FixO in *fixNI* bacteroids where *fixNOQP2* genes might be expressed could actually be due to a technical limitation, given that overall sensitivity of the arrays is better than the haem-staining protein detection. Therefore, on the long term, other copies could replace copy one through lower expression rates. Alternatively, after 7 weeks, some recombination could take place with the remaining copies that complement a native-like *fixNOQP1* operon. It might be also possible that other terminal oxidases such as the high-affinity *bd*-type oxidase or the *cyo* quinol oxidase are also involved in supporting nitrogenase activity in 7-week-old plants. In this context, the *E. meliloti* chromosome contains *smc02254* and *smc02255* genes (<http://genome.kazusa.or.jp/rhizobase/>), which encode a high-affinity quinol oxidase that is likely to contribute to micro-oxic respiration in addition to or in the absence of the *cbb₃* oxidase. Furthermore, recent transcriptional studies have reported that *cyo* genes encoding a cytochrome *o* ubiquinol oxidase were induced under microaerobic conditions (Bobik *et al.* [2006](#)).

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by Fondo Europeo de Desarrollo Regional-cofinanced grant AGL2010-18607 from Ministerio de Economía y Competitividad (Spain) and by Ciencia y Tecnología para el Desarrollo [grant number 107PICO312]. Support from the Junta de Andalucía to Group BIO-275 is also acknowledged. M.J.T. was supported by a fellowship from the Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas I3P Programme.

References

- Abriata, L.A., Banci, L., Bertini, I., Ciofi-Baffoni, S., Gkazonis, P., Spyroulias, G.A., Vila, A.J. and Wang, S. (2008) Mechanism of Cu(A) assembly. *Nat Chem Biol* **4**, 599–601.
- Ampe, F., Kiss, E., Sabourdy, F. and Batut, J. (2003) Transcriptome analysis of *Sinorhizobium meliloti* during symbiosis. *Genome Biol* **4**, R15.
- Banci, L., Bertini, I., Ciofi-Baffoni, S., Katsari, E., Katsaros, N., Kubicek, K. and Mangani, S. (2005) A copper(I) protein possibly involved in the assembly of CuA center of bacterial cytochrome *c* oxidase. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*
- Barnett, M.J., Fisher, R.F., Jones, T., Komp, C., Abola, A.P., Barloy-Hubler, F., Bowser, L., Capela, D. *et al.* (2001) Nucleotide sequence and predicted functions of the entire *Sinorhizobium meliloti* pSymA megaplasmid. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* **98**, 9883–9888.
- Barnett, M.J., Toman, C.J., Fisher, R.F. and Long, S.R. (2004) A dual-genome Symbiosis Chip for coordinate study of signal exchange and development in a prokaryote-host interaction. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* **101**, 16636–16641.
- Becker, A., Berges, H., Krol, E., Bruand, C., Ruberg, S., Capela, D., Lauber, E., Meilhoc, E. *et al.* (2004) Global changes in gene expression in *Sinorhizobium meliloti* 1021 under microoxic and symbiotic conditions. *Mol Plant Microbe Interact* **17**, 292–303.
- Becker, A., Barnett, M.J., Capela, D., Dondrup, M., Kamp, P.B., Krol, E., Linke, B., Ruberg, S. *et al.* (2009) A portal for rhizobial genomes: RhizoGATE integrates a *Sinorhizobium meliloti* genome annotation update with postgenome data. *J Biotechnol* **140**, 45–50.

- Beringer, J.E. (1974). R factor transfer in *Rhizobium leguminosarum*. *J Gen Microbiol* **84**, 188–198.
- Bobik, C., Meilhoc, E. and Batut, J. (2006) FixJ: a major regulator of the oxygen limitation response and late symbiotic functions of *Sinorhizobium meliloti*. *J Bacteriol* **188**, 4890–4902.
- Bueno, E., Mesa, S., Bedmar, E.J., Richardson, D.J. and Delgado, M.J. (2012) Bacterial adaptation of respiration from oxic to microoxic and anoxic conditions: redox control. *Antioxid Redox Signal* **16**, 819–852.
- Buschmann, S., Warkentin, E., Xie, H., Langer, J.D., Ermler, U. and Michel, H. (2010) The structure of *cbb₃* cytochrome oxidase provides insights into proton pumping. *Science* **329**, 327–330.
- Cosseau, C. and Batut, J. (2004) Genomics of the *ccoNOQP*-encoded *cbb₃* oxidase complex in bacteria. *Arch Microbiol* **181**, 89–96.
- Cosseau, C., Garnerone, A.M. and Batut, J. (2002) The *fixM* flavoprotein modulates inhibition by AICAR or 5'AMP of respiratory and nitrogen fixation gene expression in *Sinorhizobium meliloti*. *Mol Plant Microbe Interact* **15**, 598–607.
- Delgado, M.J., Bedmar, E.J. and Downie, J.A. (1998) Genes involved in the formation and assembly of rhizobial cytochromes and their role in symbiotic nitrogen fixation. *Adv Microb Physiol* **40**, 191–231.
- Deshmukh, M., Turkarlan, S., Astor, D., Valkova-Valchanova, M. and Daldal, F. (2003) The dithiol:disulfide oxidoreductases DsbA and DsbB of *Rhodobacter capsulatus* are not directly involved in cytochrome c biogenesis, but their inactivation restores the cytochrome c biogenesis defect of CcdA-null mutants. *J Bacteriol* **185**, 3361–3372.
- Dixon, R. and Kahn, D. (2004) Genetic regulation of biological nitrogen fixation. *Nat Rev Microbiol* **2**, 621–631.
- Downie, J.A. (2005) Legume haemoglobins: symbiotic nitrogen fixation needs bloody nodules. *Curr Biol* **15**, R196–R198.
- Ekici, S., Pawlik, G., Lohmeyer, E., Koch, H.G. and Daldal, F. (2012) Biogenesis of *cbb₃*-type cytochrome c oxidase in *Rhodobacter capsulatus*. *Biochim Biophys Acta* **1817**, 898–910.
- Fischer, H.M. (1994) Genetic regulation of nitrogen fixation in rhizobia. *Microbiol Rev* **58**, 352–386.
- Galibert, F., Finan, T.M., Long, S.R., Puhler, A., Abola, P., Ampe, F., Barloy-Hubler, F., Barnett, M.J. *et al.* (2001) The composite genome of the legume symbiont *Sinorhizobium meliloti*. *Science* **293**, 668–672.
- Garnerone, A.M., Cabanes, D., Foussard, M., Boistard, P. and Batut, J. (1999) Inhibition of the FixL sensor kinase by the FixT protein in *Sinorhizobium meliloti*. *J Biol Chem* **274**, 32500–32506.
- Girard, L., Brom, S., Davalos, A., Lopez, O., Soberon, M. and Romero, D. (2000) Differential regulation of *fixN*-reiterated genes in *Rhizobium etli* by a novel *fixL*-*fixK* cascade. *Mol Plant Microbe Interact* **13**, 1283–1292.

- Granados-Baeza, M.J., Gomez-Hernandez, N., Mora, Y., Delgado, M.J., Romero, D. and Girard, L. (2007) Novel reiterated Fnr-type proteins control the production of the symbiotic terminal oxidase *cbb₃* in *Rhizobium etli* CFN42. *Mol Plant Microbe Interact* **20**, 1241–1249.
- Jones, K.M., Kobayashi, H., Davies, B.W., Taga, M.E. and Walker, G.C. (2007) How rhizobial symbionts invade plants: the *Sinorhizobium-Medicago* model. *Nat Rev Microbiol* **5**, 619–633.
- Krol, E. and Becker, A. (2004) Global transcriptional analysis of the phosphate starvation response in *Sinorhizobium meliloti* strains 1021 and 2011. *Mol Genet Genomics* **272**, 1–17.
- Kulajta, C., Thumfart, J.O., Haid, S., Daldal, F. and Koch, H.G. (2006) Multi-step assembly pathway of the *cbb₃*-type cytochrome c oxidase complex. *J Mol Biol* **355**, 989–1004.
- Leonard, L.T. (1943) A simple assembly for use in the testing of cultures of Rhizobia. *J Bacteriol* **45**, 523–527.
- Mandon, K., Kaminski, P.A., Mougel, C., Desnoues, N., Dreyfus, B. and Elmerich, C. (1993) Role of the *fixGHI* region of *Azorhizobium caulinodans* in free-living and symbiotic nitrogen fixation. *FEMS Microbiol Lett* **114**, 185–189.
- Mandon, K., Kaminski, P.A. and Elmerich, C. (1994) Functional analysis of the *fixNOQP* region of *Azorhizobium caulinodans*. *J Bacteriol* **176**, 2560–2568.
- Marroqui, S., Zorreguieta, A., Santamaria, C., Temprano, F., Soberon, M., Megias, M. and Downie, J.A. (2001) Enhanced symbiotic performance by *Rhizobium tropici* glycogen synthase mutants. *J Bacteriol* **183**, 854–864.
- Meade, H.M., Long, S.R., Ruvkun, G.B., Brown, S.E. and Ausubel, F.M. (1982) Physical and genetic characterization of symbiotic and auxotrophic mutants of *Rhizobium meliloti* induced by transposon Tn5 mutagenesis. *J Bacteriol* **149**, 114–122.
- Meilhoc, E., Cam, Y., Skapski, A. and Bruand, C. (2010) The response to nitric oxide of the nitrogen-fixing symbiont *Sinorhizobium meliloti*. *Mol Plant Microbe Interact* **23**, 748–759.
- Mesa, S., Alche Jd, J.D., Bedmar, E. and Delgado, M.J. (2004) Expression of *nir*, *nor* and *nos* denitrification genes from *Bradyrhizobium japonicum* in soybean root nodules. *Physiol Plant* **120**, 205–211.
- Miller, J.H. (1972) *Experiments in Molecular Genetics*. New York: Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press.
- Minchin, F.R., James, E.K. and Becana, M. (2008). Oxygen diffusion, production of reactive oxygen and nitrogen species, and antioxidants in legume nodules. In *Nitrogen-Fixing Leguminous Symbioses*. ed. M.J. Dilworth, E.K. James, J.I. Sprent and W.E. Newton 321–362. Dordrecht, the Netherlands: Springer Science.
- Oldroyd, G.E. and Downie, J.A. (2008) Coordinating nodule morphogenesis with rhizobial infection in legumes. *Annu Rev Plant Biol* **59**, 519–546.
- Oldroyd, G.E., Murray, J.D., Poole, P.S. and Downie, J.A. (2011) The rules of engagement in the legume-rhizobial symbiosis. *Annu Rev Genet* **45**, 119–144.

- Pawlik, G., Kulajta, C., Sachelaru, I., Schroder, S., Waidner, B., Hellwig, P., Daldal, F. and Koch, H.G. (2010) The putative assembly factor CcoH is stably associated with the *cbb₃*-type cytochrome oxidase. *J Bacteriol* **192**, 6378–6389.
- Peters, A., Kulajta, C., Pawlik, G., Daldal, F. and Koch, H.G. (2008) Stability of the *cbb₃*-type cytochrome oxidase requires specific CcoQ-CcoP interactions. *J Bacteriol* **190**, 5576–5586.
- Pitcher, R.S. and Watmough, N.J. (2004) The bacterial cytochrome *cbb₃* oxidases. *Biochim Biophys Acta* **1655**, 388–399.
- Preisig, O., Anthamatten, D. and Hennecke, H. (1993) Genes for a microaerobically induced oxidase complex in *Bradyrhizobium japonicum* are essential for a nitrogen-fixing endosymbiosis. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* **90**, 3309–3313.
- Preisig, O., Zufferey, R., Thony-Meyer, L., Appleby, C.A. and Hennecke, H. (1996) A high-affinity *cbb₃*-type cytochrome oxidase terminates the symbiosis-specific respiratory chain of *Bradyrhizobium japonicum*. *J Bacteriol* **178**, 1532–1538.
- Prentki, P. and Krisch, H.M. (1984) In vitro insertional mutagenesis with a selectable DNA fragment. *Gene* **29**, 303–313.
- Renalier, M.H., Batut, J., Ghai, J., Terzaghi, B., Gherardi, M., David, M., Garnerone, A.M., Vasse, J. *et al.* (1987) A new symbiotic cluster on the pSym megaplasmid of *Rhizobium meliloti* 2011 carries a functional fix gene repeat and a *nod* locus. *J Bacteriol* **169**, 2231–2238.
- Reyrat, J.M., David, M., Blonski, C., Boistard, P. and Batut, J. (1993) Oxygen-regulated in vitro transcription of *Rhizobium meliloti nifA* and *fixK* genes. *J Bacteriol* **175**, 6867–6872.
- Rigaud, J. and Puppo, A. (1975) Indole-3-acetic-acid catabolism by soybean bacteroids. *J Gen Microbiol* **88**, 223–228.
- Robertsen, B.K., Aman, P., Darvill, A.G., McNeil, M. and Albersheim, P. (1981) Host-Symbiont Interactions: V. The structure of acidic extracellular polysaccharides secreted by *Rhizobium leguminosarum* and *Rhizobium trifolii*. *Plant Physiol* **67**, 389–400.
- Sambrook, J. and Russell, D. (2004) *Molecular Cloning: A Laboratory Manual*, 2nd edn. Cold Spring Harbor, NY: Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press.
- Schäfer, A., Tauch, A., Jäger, W., Kalinowski, J., Thierbach, G. and Puhler, A. (1994) Small mobilizable multi-purpose cloning vectors derived from the *Escherichia coli* plasmids pK18 and pK19: selection of defined deletions in the chromosome of *Corynebacterium glutamicum*. *Gene* **145**, 69–73.
- Schlüter, A., Patschkowski, T., Quandt, J., Selinger, L.B., Weidner, S., Kramer, M., Zhou, L., Hynes, M.F. *et al.* (1997) Functional and regulatory analysis of the two copies of the *fixNOQP* operon of *Rhizobium leguminosarum* strain VF39. *Mol Plant Microbe Interact* **10**, 605–616.
- Serventi, F., Youard, Z.A., Murset, V., Huwiler, S., Buhler, D., Richter, M., Luchsinger, R., Fischer, H.M. *et al.* (2012) Copper starvation-inducible protein for cytochrome oxidase biogenesis in *Bradyrhizobium japonicum*. *J Biol Chem* **287**, 38812–38823.

- Simon, L.D., Randolph, B., Irwin, N. and Binkowski, G. (1983) Stabilization of proteins by a bacteriophage T4 gene cloned in *Escherichia coli*. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* **80**, 2059–2062.
- Swem, D.L., Swem, L.R., Setterdahl, A. and Bauer, C.E. (2005) Involvement of SenC in assembly of cytochrome c oxidase in *Rhodobacter capsulatus*. *J Bacteriol* **187**, 8081–8087.
- Thony-Meyer, L., Stax, D. and Hennecke, H. (1989) An unusual gene cluster for the cytochrome *bc1* complex in *Bradyrhizobium japonicum* and its requirement for effective root nodule symbiosis. *Cell* **57**, 683–697.
- Trzebiatowski, J.R., Ragatz, D.M. and de Bruijn, F.J. (2001) Isolation and regulation of *Sinorhizobium meliloti* 1021 loci induced by oxygen limitation. *Appl Environ Microbiol* **67**, 3728–3731.
- Uchiumi, T., Ohwada, T., Itakura, M., Mitsui, H., Nukui, N., Dawadi, P., Kaneko, T., Tabata, S. *et al.* (2004) Expression islands clustered on the symbiosis island of the *Mesorhizobium loti* genome. *J Bacteriol* **186**, 2439–2448.
- Vargas, C., McEwan, A.G. and Downie, J.A. (1993) Detection of *c*-type cytochromes using enhanced chemiluminescence. *Anal Biochem* **209**, 323–326.
- Wu, G., Delgado, M.J., Vargas, C., Davies, A.E., Poole, R.K. and Downie, J.A. (1996) The cytochrome *bc1* complex but not CycM is necessary for symbiotic nitrogen fixation by *Rhizobium leguminosarum*. *Microbiology* **142**, 3381–3388.
- Yurgel, S.N., Berrocal, J., Wilson, C. and Kahn, M.L. (2007) Pleiotropic effects of mutations that alter the *Sinorhizobium meliloti* cytochrome *c* respiratory system. *Microbiology* **153**, 399–410.